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Exegetical Analysis of Rapture in the Light of 1 Thessalonians 4:15-18

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Abstract

This study was prompted by the carefree attitude of the postmodern Christians towards biblical teachings, most especially, rapture. The paper is an exegetical analysis of Paul's Eschatological Discourse in 1 Thessalonians 4: 15-18. The paper aims at using the eschatological teachings of Paul in 1Thessalonians 4:15-18 to challenge the postmodern society to be rapture-ready in spite of the obstacles placed on their way by the negative traits of postmodernism. The paper commences with a brief introduction on the negative features of the postmodern world that encourages the postmodern man's complacent attitudes towards rapture. The next focal points of the paper are the texts surrounding the main text where Apostle Paul encouraged the Thessalonian church to build up their faith, love and grace for holiness (1Thessalonian 4:13-14). The surrounding texts also present Paul's transition to eschatological discourse and the purpose was to comfort those alive who were grieving over the dead because they were confused. The paper also touches the source of Paul's eschatological discourse: the eschatological discourse of Jesus Christ. A step-by-step procedure of rapture is presented. The paper draws

inferences for application for the postmodern church from the discourse analysis and closes with recommendations.

Keywords: Amillennial, Exegesis, Postmodern, Postmillennial, Premillennial, Rapture

Introduction

Postmodernism is a term used to philosophically describe the current era which came after the age of modernism. The philosophical concept seems to undermine the reality and significance of rapture. The dangers of postmodernism can be perceived as a downward spiral that kicks off with the rejection of absolute truth, which births a loss of distinctions in religious and faith issues culminating in a philosophy of religious pluralism. It upholds the tenet that no faith or religion is objectively true and as such, no one can claim his or her religion is true and another is false. The Christian faith and all its tenets, rapture inclusive, are at a great disadvantage due to the adverse effects of postmodern ideologies. Hence, this paper explores rapture in the postmodern context in the light of 1 Thessalonians 4:15-18.

According to Stewart (2020) the rapture of the church is a term that is commonly used for the sudden removal of genuine believers from the earth, to meet their Lord in the air. Explicating further, he says that at some point in the future, those Christians who are alive will have their mortal bodies transformed into incorruptible, immortal bodies as taught in 1Cor. 15. Immediately before this happens, the believers who have died will be raised from the dead and will also receive a new body as they meet Christ in the air. According to Scripture all of this will occur in a moment, in a twinkling, or in a blink, of an eye.

Wenstrom, Jr, (2021) in his own definition and explanation of the term rapture, says it is taken from the Latin term *rapio*, “caught up” that is used to translate the Greek verb *harpazō* (ἁρπάζω), which appears in 1 Thessalonians 4:17. In this verse, according to him, the word means to “snatch, seize, forcibly remove something, to seize by force with the purpose of removing and is translated “will be caught up” by the Easy Standard Version (ESV) and New American Standard Bible 1995 (NASB95) and “will be suddenly caught up” by the New English Translation Bible 2005 (NET Bible).

Shedding light on the concept, Stewart (2020) says that the doctrine of the rapture of the church is mainly for the genuine believers in Jesus Christ

(not merely people who have a church membership or affiliation). According to Wenstrom (2021), the term rapture is used by students of prophecy and eschatology to describe the doctrine which is taught in the New Testament. He makes it clear that the term “rapture” is not found in the original languages of Scripture; it is only used by theologians to describe a doctrine that is taught in the Bible.

Exegesis of 1 Thessalonians 4:15-18

Greek Translation

15 Τοῦτο γάρ ὑμῖν λέγομεν ἐν λόγῳ κυρίου, ὅτι ἡμεῖς οἱ ζῶντες οἱ περιλειπόμενοι εἰς τὴν παρουσίαν τοῦ κυρίου, οὐ μὴ φθάσωμεν τοὺς κοιμηθέντας. 16. Ὅτι αὐτὸς ὁ κύριος ἐν κελεύσματι, ἐν φωνῇ ἀρχαγγέλου, καὶ ἐν σάλπιγγι θεοῦ, καταβήσεται ἀπ’ οὐρανοῦ, καὶ οἱ νεκροὶ ἐν χριστῷ ἀναστήσονται πρῶτον · 17. ἔπειτα ἡμεῖς οἱ ζῶντες, οἱ περιλειπόμενοι, ἅμα σὺν αὐτοῖς ἀρπαγησόμεθα ἐν νεφέλαις εἰς ἀπάντησιν τοῦ κυρίου εἰς ἀέρα · καὶ οὕτως πάντοτε σὺν κυρίῳ ἐσόμεθα. 18. Ὡστε παρακαλεῖτε ἀλλήλους ἐν τοῖς λόγοις τούτοις.

Transliteration

15 *Tóuto gár humín légomen en lógoo Kuríou, hótí heemeís hoi zoóntes hoi perileipómenoi eis teen parousían tou Kuríou, ou-meé fthásoomen toús koimeethéntas 16 hótí autós ho Kúrios en keleúsmati en fooneé archangéλου καὶ en sálpingi Theoú katabeésetai ap ouranou kaí hoi nekroí en Christoó anasteésontai proton 17 épeita heemeís hoi zoóntes hoi perileipómenoi háma sún autoís harpageesómetha en nefélais eis apánteessin tou Kuríou eis aéra Kaí hóutoos pántote sún Kuríoo esómetha 18 Hoóste parakaleíte alleélous en toís lógois toútois* Biblesoft, (2006.)

English Translation

15 According to the Lord's own word, we tell you that we who are still alive, who are left till the coming of the Lord, will certainly not precede those who have fallen asleep. 16 For the Lord himself will come down from heaven, with a loud command, with the voice of the archangel and with the trumpet call of God, and the dead in Christ will rise first. 17 After that, we who are still alive and are left will be caught up together with them in the clouds to meet the Lord in

the air. And so we will be with the Lord forever. 18 Therefore encourage each other with these words. (NIV)

Surrounding Texts

Preceding chapter is an encouragement to the church for their faith and love and an expression of gratitude for the joy they give them. Paul says that they are 'really living' (3.8) but gives them room to grow as he prays for the love to increase and overflow for each other and for everyone else (3.12). Paul used the medium to call the church of the Thessalonians to a higher standard. Having exhorted his audience to always abound in holiness, with a warning against ungodly lives (4:1-8), apostle Paul urged his audience to always abound in love and avoid idleness (4:12). The apostle concludes with words of comfort to those who mourned for their relations and friends who had died in the Lord (verses 13-18). Paul exhorts this church to do things they are already doing, or that they already know. This is seen in multiple verses:

4:1a *'We instructed you how to live in order to please God, as in fact you are living'*

4:2 *'You know what instructions we gave you by the authority of the Lord Jesus'*

4:6b *'as we have already told you and warned you'*

4:10a *'And in fact, you do love all the brothers throughout Macedonia'*

4:10b *'Yet we urge you, brothers, to do so more and more'*

There had been distress among the Thessalonian Christians regarding those who had died, hence, the cause of this distress cannot be said emphatically. Some scholars are of the opinion that this brethren are being misled by some false teachers. The purpose of Paul's transition to eschatological discourse was to comfort those alive who were grieving over the dead because they were confused. In verse 13 Paul addresses the topic about those who 'have fallen asleep' (*koimōmenōn*). The Greek word *koimōmenōn* is in reference to people who are 'asleep to death'. *Koimaō*, a common word for sleep, was often used as a euphemism for death in Greek, Jewish, and Christian writings as well as in Paul's epistles. There is nothing in the context to indicate that Paul used the word here in any way other than the conventional fashion. To read the term as an ontological assertion regarding the state of believers in the interim between death and resurrection is to import ideas not supported by this context (Michael Martin, 1995). Paul tells those alive not to

(*lypēsthe*) meaning grieve, or sorrow and not be like ἔχω μὴ ἐλπίς (*echo mē elpis*) meaning have (*echo*) no (*me*) hope (*elpis*). They were not to act like hopeless people. The Greek word Paul uses for hope is *elpida* which means a hope, expectation, or confidence.

Paul states the basis of this Christian hope in First Thessalonians 4:14. If we believe that Jesus died and rose, we can believe also in the resurrection of the dead Christians (v. 14). Paul asserts that those who died in the Lord by the virtue of Christ's resurrection, would be resurrected unto eternal life and blessedness. Because Christ rose, so God will bring with Jesus those who have fallen asleep in him. As stated by Martin 'The God who raised Jesus will also raise Jesus' followers. It is Jesus' resurrection that validates the gospel and guarantees the believers' resurrection (cf. 1 Corinthians 15:17–20) (Martin, 1995).

It is pertinent to indicate that the concern of this section is on verses 15-18. However, this text under study will not be exposed in isolation, the preceding and the subsequent text would be referenced. Epistle of Paul to the Thessalonians Church was basically a treatise for encouragement and exhortation to the Christians.

Exegetical Study

Verse 15 begins with τοῦτο γὰρ ὑμῖν λέγομεν ἐν λόγῳ κυρίου, (*τούτο γάρ ἡμῖν λέγομεν ἐν λόγῳ Κυρίου*), meaning for this we say unto you by the word of the Lord. *Toutu meaning this and gar meaning for, which can be translated for this*. Τοῦτο is the near demonstrative pronoun used to call attention to a designated person or object, often with special emphasis *this* (Matt 3.17); (1) used as an adjective *this* in Luke 2.25); (2) used as a substantive *this man, this woman, this thing, this one* (Matt 12.23); (3) both adjectival and substantival forms may be used as a contemptuous sneer: οὗ (*ou*). *this fellow* (Matt. 26.71); οὗ. ὁ τελώνης (*ou o telonhs*) *this tax collector* (LU 18.11); (4) used resumptively to give special emphasis to a person or thing previously mentioned *the very one* (Act 7.36); *toutu* is used cataphorically to refer to what follows, introducing a statement of purpose, result, condition *this (is what I mean), this (namely)*. □□□ (*gar*) as used here is a "primary particle; properly assigning a *reason* (used in argument, explanation or intensification; often with other particles): - and, as, because (that), but, even, for indeed, no doubt, seeing, then, therefore, verily, what, why, yet." E-Sword As used by Paul *lēgomen (we say) en (by) logoo (word)*

Kuriou (of the Lord). According to the Lord's own word, here implies that what he (Paul) “speaks, was either by some tradition from others, or an invention of his own; and that is the ground enough for faith, to which our judgment and reason ought to be captivated (Matthew Poole, 1990). Paul was declaring the mind of the Lord. According to Martin,

Several revelations are made in the verses that follow: (a) the dead will rise and join the Lord prior to the living joining him (v. 15), (b) the Lord's descent will be with a loud command, with the voice of the archangel, and with the trumpet call of God (v. 16), (c) those who were dead and the those living will be caught up together (v. 17), and (d) all believers will be with the Lord forever (v. 17). Paul validated these assertions with an appeal to divine authority (v. 15). Whether the Lord's own word (*en logō kyriou*) was a reference to the teachings of the earthly Jesus or to later revelation, it confirmed the accuracy of what follows. In the statement that initiates v. 15, literally, For this we say to you (cf. NASB), the for indicates that the word of the Lord that follows is the basis for the assurances given in v. 14. This looks forward to the teaching expressed in vv. 15b–17. Paul assured the church that what he was about to say was according to the Lord's own word. It was not human speculation but divine revelation (cf. 4:8). This might have originated as a revelation from the exalted Jesus (either to Paul or to another prophet), but if this is so, the very nature of the event precludes our knowing about it without more background than the apostle provided. And apart from a clear knowledge of the source of the word we cannot know whether the content of vv. 15–17 is a quotation or a summation of the Lord's teaching (Martin, 1995).

This is followed by *ὅτι ἡμεῖς οἱ ζῶντες οἱ περιλειπόμενοι εἰς τὴν παρουσίαν τοῦ κυρίου, οὐ μὴ φθάσωμεν τοὺς κοιμηθέντας* (*hóti heemeís hoi zoóntes hoi perileipómenoi eis teen parousían tou Kuríou ou-meé fthásoomen toús.*) *koimeethéntas*) translated in the NIV as “we tell you that we who are still alive, who are left till the coming of the Lord, will certainly not precede those who have fallen asleep.” The phrase we who are still alive (*heemeís hoi zoóntes hoi perileipómenoi*) could imply Paul's hoping to be alive at rapture. Hendriksen and Kistemaker notes that the fact that Paul says “we”, does not necessarily mean that he expected to be among those who would still be living at Christ's return. He says we because right now he, Silas, Timothy, the readers, are among those believers still living on earth. He

immediately modifies this by interpreting it to mean: those who are left (when he comes),” in order to indicate that only God knows whom they may be. Paul knows that the second coming will not take place immediately (II Thess. 2:2); and while he was in Thessalonica, this element in his teaching regarding the last things was not neglected (II Thess. 2:5), (Hendriksen & Kistemaker, 2004).

Paul asserted in v. 15b that we who are alive at the time of the *parousia* will not precede those who have died. The subject “we” is emphatic and is clarified by the clause who are still alive, who are left till the coming of the Lord. A point of considerable interest to those seeking to understand Pauline eschatology is whether or not the fact that Paul used the first person, we, meant that he expected the Lord to return in his lifetime. The assumption has generally been that this was indeed the case. Others find evidence that Paul initially expected the Lord to come during his lifetime but that as the years passed revised his position and accepted the possibility that the Lord’s return might be further in the future than he originally anticipated (Martin, 1995). As cited by Martin Witherington, on the other hand, makes a strong case that Paul believed the end could come at any time but did not presume to predict its timing. When speaking of the end and envisioning himself in relation to it, Paul normally cast himself in the category of the living since he was alive at the time he wrote, but this was a convention, not a prediction (Martin, 1995).

Verse 16 begins with a *hoti* (for) clause, indicating that what follows was presented as verification of the assertion (vv. 14–15) that the dead will participate in the *parousia*, meaning coming. The sequence of events is presented in four steps. First, the Lord will descend, and then the dead will rise (v. 16). Following that the living will be caught up, and finally all believers will be together with the Lord forever (v. 17). The point clearly made is that those who die before the *parousia* will participate in it along with those who are alive when he comes, and both will enjoy the life with the Lord that follows. The two primary statements in v. 16 are the Lord himself will come down and the dead in Christ will rise. The disciples witnessed Jesus’ ascent into the clouds and were told he would return in the same way (Acts 1:9–11; cf. Mark 13:26). Stephen saw the heavens open and Jesus, the Son of Man, standing at the right hand of God (Acts 7:55–56). The Thessalonians demonstrated their faith by eagerly awaiting the coming of Jesus, the Son of God, from heaven (1 Thessalonians 1:3, 10). Eventually

the long-awaited Jesus will descend this time not as a babe but with grand display and heavenly entourage as befits the heavenly Lord himself. He comes with a loud command, with the voice of the archangel and with the trumpet call of God. The three phrases are parallel, each introduced by the preposition $\square v$ (*en* meaning with). The second two statements are joined by “and” (*kai*), which Frame takes as an indication that the latter two phrases explain the first (Martin, 1995). He suggests the translation at a command, namely, at an archangel’s voice and at a trumpet of God. But the presence of the *kai* does not make this certain, and the three events also may be viewed as separate and distinct or as a threefold description of a single occurrence. (Martin, 1995)

The shouted command $\kappa\epsilon\lambda\epsilon\upsilon\sigma\mu\alpha\tau\iota$, *keleusmati* Hendriksen and Kistemaker comment that ($\kappa\epsilon\lambda\epsilon\upsilon\sigma\mu\alpha$, in the New Testament occurring only here, but see Proverbs 30:27 in LXX) is originally the order which an officer shouts to his troops, a hunter to his dog, a charioteer to his horses, or a ship-master to his rovers. In the present connection it is clearly the command of the Lord, as he leaves heaven, for the dead to rise. Note the context: those who have fallen asleep shall not be at disadvantage (verse 15), for with a shout... the Lord himself will descend from heaven, and the dead in Christ will rise... (verse 16). Just as even here and now the voice of the Son of God is life-giving, causing those who are spiritually dead to be quickened (John 5:25), so also when he comes back “all who are in the tombs will hear his voice and will come out (John 5:28). The command, therefore, is definitely his own, proceeding from his lips. It is not a command issued for him, but an order given by him (Hendriksen & Kistemaker, 2004). The shout, the voice, and the trumpet may be different figures for the same event. The language reflects the *theophanic* passages of the Old Testament; Joel 2:1ff.; especially verse 11. The dead in Christ (16); cf. verse 14; 1 Corinthians 15:18; Revelation 14:13. Shall be caught up (17); Gr. *Harpagesómetha*, Latin *rapiemur*, whence the event is sometimes called the ‘rapture’ or snatching away of the saints. In the clouds (17); cf. Daniel 7:13; Mark. 13:26; 14:62; revelation 1:7. To meet the Lord (17); Greek *eis apánteessin tou Kuríou*. When a dignitary paid an official visit or *parousia* to a city in Hellenistic times, the action of the leading citizens in going out to meet him and escorting him on the final stage of his journey was called *apánteesis*; it is similarly used in Mathew 25:6; Acts 28:15. So the Lord is pictured as escorted to the earth by his people- those newly raised from death and those

who have remained alive. And so shall we ever be with the Lord (17); the climax of blessedness. But no man knows the times and the seasons (v. 1). (M.A Davidson)

The expression to meet (εἰς ἀπάντησιν, *eis apanthsin*) was used in connection with an official welcome accorded to a newly arrived dignitary. No doubt the welcoming idea is also included in the expression as used in 1 Thessalonians 4:17. That all believers, the raised as well as (and together) changed, shall ascend to meet the Lord in the air is clearly taught here (Hendriksen & Kistemaker, 2004).

All believers shall be with the Lord never to be separated from him. Paul stated emphatically that at the *parousia* the living will certainly not precede those who have fallen asleep. This may indicate that the church feared that the dead would be raised at some time after the *parousia* and so miss the glories of that day. But it is far from certain that this was the problem in the church. It seems safer to find the emphasis in Paul's words on his statement of the problem in v. 14 and his climactic statement in v. 17. In these verses the emphasis does not seem to fall on the sequence of the participation of the living and the dead but on the understanding that the dead will in fact participate in the *parousia*. This need not mean that Paul previously had not taught this in Thessalonica. The problem may well have been the difficulty of appropriating the doctrine of the resurrection into the way that enabled these Gentile believers to manage the trauma of death. Paul wanted to spare believers the sorrow of hopeless loss so common to the pagan world. He did so by reiterating truths in traditional language and applying them to immediate needs (Martin, 1995). Some of the Thessalonian Christians may have died shortly after receiving the gospel. Yet the letter was written only a few months after the initial evangelization of the city.... The short time between the evangelization of the city and the writing of this letter would militate against the possibility of multiple deaths in the congregation in the interim. Although the letter refers to persecutions, there is no reference to deaths in Christ's service. Considering the extremes to which Paul went to affirm the faith of the church, failure on his part to highlight faithfulness to the point of death seems incredible. The references to those who have fallen asleep are references to all the faithful who had died, not specifically Thessalonian Christians who had died. (Martin, 1995). A loud command translates a single noun used only here in the New Testament. It was relatively common in nonbiblical Greek, and in general it

indicates an order or a signal given to subordinates. Neither the origin nor the nature of this particular command is clear. The command could be issued from Jesus to the dead to arise (cf. John 5:28–29), from Jesus to his entourage to proceed (cf. 2 Thessalonians 1:7), or from the archangel as either a cry of announcement (like the trumpet, cf. Revelation 1:10) or an order to the heavenly host. The phrase ἐν φωνῇ ἀρχαγγέλου (*en fooneé archangéλου*) with the voice of the archangel connotes the involvement of the heavenly host. Mark also recorded that Jesus will come with the holy angels (Mark 8:38) and that he will send them to gather his elect from the four winds (13:26–27). The reference to an archangel implies a ranking of heavenly beings that was a common feature of Hellenistic Judaism. Although New Testament authors did not involve themselves in the elaborate naming and ranking of the heavenly host in general, the New Testament does refer twice to archangels (here and Jude 9) and names two angels. Michael is called an archangel (Jude 9; cf. Daniel 10:13; 12:1), and Gabriel is an angel who stands in the presence of God (Luke 1:19). Implied with the use of the term archangel is both status and the existence (if not the presence) of subordinates. The Lord is not alone but is accompanied by an angelic entourage. The archangel functions either as the herald proclaiming remarkable news the arrival of the Lord or calls the angelic army to advance with the Lord. (D. Michael Martin) 97 The term archangel or chief angel occurs only here and in Jude 9. In the later passage Michael is the archangel. It is possible that Michael is the only archangel or one of the archangels.

The Lord's descent is also with the trumpet call of God. A trumpet call was used for a variety of purposes in the ancient orient but was not much used as a musical instrument; its main task was to give signals. It could herald a great event or issue a warning to the people (1 Samuel 13:3; Jeremiah 4:5). It was often used in military settings (Josh 6:4–5; Judges 6:34; Nehemiah 4:19–20; cf. 1 Corinthians 14:8). It signaled the Hebrews' encounter with Yahweh at Sinai (Exodus 19:16, 19) and was used as part of the pageantry at religious festivals (Numbers 10:10; Leviticus 23:24; 25:8; Psalms 81:3; cf. Mathew 6:2). Finally, both Jewish and Christian images of God's arrival at the end to gather his people, execute judgment, and establish his kingdom include the announcement of his arrival with the trumpet (Isaiah 27:13; Zechariah 9:14; Ezra 6:23; *Apoc. Mos.* 22; Revelation 8:2–12; 9:1, 13; 11:15). Used in conjunction the voice of the archangel and the shout of command

and the trumpet depict a grand fanfare. No one will be able to miss the event. No one will fail to realize that something remarkable is about to occur (Martin, 1997).

At the command, the voice, and the trumpet, the dead in Christ will rise. There is no mention of non-Christian dead in these verses (cf. 2:16; 2 Thessalonians 1:6–10). Likewise there is no discussion of the resurrection body or of the manner in which the living are translated (cf. 1 Corinthians 15:35–54). Paul was presenting information to comfort a church grieving like those who had no hope. So that which claimed all his attention was the fact that the resurrected Christian dead will join with the Christian living at the parousia and together they will share the presence of the Lord on that day and forever. First is the final word of v. 16. After that (*epeita*), the first word of v. 17, does not have a strong temporal sense. It indicates a sequence of events, but almost immediately the two events are blended into a single occurrence as the resurrected dead join the living and both are caught up ... to meet the Lord (Martin, 1995).

4:17 ἀρπάζω fut. ἀρπάσω (*arpaso*); ἤρπασα (*arpasa*) is used “as forcibly taking someone or something *snatch, seize, take away* (John 6.15); (2) as the action of thieves and wild beasts *steal, carry off, drag away* (John 10.12); (3) of seed already sown *carry off, snatch away* (Mathew 13.19); (4) of an ecstatic vision or experience *catch up or away* (2C 12.2); (5) ἄ. in 11.12 has two possible meanings: (a) *seize on eagerly, appropriate* (the kingdom); (b) *attack and seize* (the kingdom) as a violent or forcible person would do; since ἄ. is used with βιάζεται (*suffer violently, be treated violently*) and βιασταί (*violent people*), the second is preferable (Bibleworks) The verb caught up (*harpazō*) is the same one found in Acts 8:39 when the Spirit suddenly took Philip away and when Paul was caught up to the third heaven (2 Corinthian 12:2–4). The subject we is modified by who are still alive and are left (the identical clause in v. 15). Will be caught up is modified by three phrases: together with them (i.e., the resurrected saints), in the clouds, and to meet the Lord in the air. The first phrase, together with them (*hama sun autois*), refers to those Christians who have been resurrected. Though *hama* (at the same time) used with *sun* (with) seems redundant, in this context the force of the preposition *sun* is strengthened by the preceding *hama*. This emphasis on the unity of the event for the living and the dead stresses two points. First, the living have no advantage over the dead in the end. Both groups will experience reunion with the Lord together. Second, the dead and

the living will themselves be reunited a reunion that will know no end. For we will be with the Lord forever. Martin Note that the latin verb *rapio* was used to translate harpaz, and from this derives the use of English term “rapture” for the event described in vv. 16-17.(D. Michael Martin) 98 Followers Christ “shall be caught up, the suddenness, the swiftness, and the divine character of the power which is operative in this being snatched up are here emphasized. (Hendriksen & Kistemaker, 2004) Together all believers will be caught up in the clouds.

What happens after believers meet the Lord in the air? The conclusion of the passage, we will be with the Lord forever (v. 17), speaks to believers’ eternal state but leaps over any end-time events between parousia and eternal state. Considering Paul’s purpose of comforting believers regarding the eternal state of the dead in Christ, v. 17 provides an appropriate conclusion to the narrative. But for those interested in end-time events this conclusion seems abrupt and leaves much unsaid. The events of vv. 16–17, for instance, are not placed in a larger temporal context. Other events associated with the end, such as a period of tribulation, the judging of humanity, or a millennial reign, are not mentioned. The state of the dead who rise to meet the lord is not discussed (cf.1Corinthians 15:35–49; 2Corinthians 5:1–9), nor is the transformation of the living (cf. 1 Corinthia 15:50–58) (Martin, 1995).

The raised and the changed are caught up together in clouds to meet the Lord in the air. The event described in vv. 16–17, commonly termed the rapture, holds a prominent place in all eschatological schemes. But it is not understood in the same way in all of them. Postmillennial and amillennial perspectives generally understand the rapture as a part of the day of the Lord when Jesus will return to gather his people to him and execute judgment on all (cf. 5:1–11). This event is variously termed the coming (*parousia*), the revelation (*apokalypsis*), or the appearance (*epiphaneia*) of the Lord. Also in some forms of premillennialism it is believed that the church will remain on the earth until the final judgment (including a period of severe tribulation near the very end). For these the coming of the Lord, the rapture of the church, and the final judgment are all facets of a single event at the end of time (Martin, 1995). In some premillennial schemes, however, the rapture is separated from the day of the Lord by the great tribulation, a seven-year period of intense, unbridled evil. Adherents to this perspective argue that the church will not remain on the earth during this

time of the tribulation. Rather, the Lord will remove (or rapture) his followers either at the beginning of the tribulation or at its midpoint. Such a scheme separates the rapture from the *parousia* by several years.

Although we cannot settle such far-reaching matters in this context, we must note that our present passage does not seem to present the event depicted in vv. 16–17 as one preceding and separate from the *parousia*, the day of the Lord (cf. 5:4–9). First, in v. 15 Paul explicitly termed the event he was describing the coming (*parousia*) of the Lord and linked the same term with final judgment (2 Thessalonians 2:8; cf. 1 Thessalonians 2:19). Since Paul did not predict two *parousias*, then the one event must encompass both the gathering of the church and final judgment. Second, v. 17 does not require the removal of the church from the world. It is in fact open-ended, describing nothing beyond the gathering of the church other than the fact of continuing in the presence of the Lord.

4:18 Paul concludes the text with *Ὡστε παρακαλεῖτε ἀλλήλους ἐν τοῖς λόγοις τούτοις* (*Hooste parakaleite alleélous en toís lógois touútois*, meaning ‘therefore encourage each other with these words’). The term *parakaleite* is from the term *παρακαλέω* (*parakaleō*) *par-ak-al-eh'-o* meaning *to call near*, that is, *invite, invoke* (by *imploration, hortation* or *consolation*): - beseech, call for, (be of good) comfort, desire, (give) exhort (-ation), intreat, pray. To *παρακαλεῖτε* (comfort) one another with these *lógois* (words) *this is the plural of logos logos* (word) which is something *said* (including the *thought*); by implication a *topic* (subject of discourse), also *reasoning* (the mental faculty) or *motive*; by extension a *computation*; specifically (with the article in John) the *Divine Expression* (that is, *Christ*): - account, cause, communication, X concerning, doctrine, fame, X have to do, intent, matter, mouth, preaching, question, reason, + reckon, remove, say (-ing), shew, X speaker, speech, talk, thing, tidings, treatise, utterance, word, work. (E-Sword)

Finally, the command to encourage each other (v. 18) could anticipate future need as easily as it could be an attempt to meet a current need. In other words vv. 13–18 may well contain admonitions appropriate to any congregation rather than being proof of a problem particular to the church at Thessalonica. The problem is the grief resulting from a death (v.13). The word of encouragement is that the Lord will reunite the living and the dead at his return (vv.14, 17). Celebrating that reunion required recounting a depiction of the *parousia* (vv.16–17). A summary description of the *parousia*

(coming) is given in vv. 16–17. Its brevity is evident. Detail is lacking. Also the sequence of events is truncated. Believers are caught up ... to meet the Lord in the air, but what happens to them after that? The modern reader (and perhaps the ancient one as well) is left wondering what comes between the gathering of the saints at the beginning of the parousia and living forever in his presence.(E-Sword).. Christians should not be grieving deaths in their community without hope. In the Gentile culture, while varied in its beliefs on the afterlife, not only balked at bodily resurrection but also lacked hope for any kind of meaningful and lasting reunion once a friend or family member died. If this life is all one has, its end in death produces considerable grief. Not so for followers of Jesus, Paul says. This is not to say that any grieving is inappropriate, for Jesus provides the example (John 11:35). Nevertheless, that grief should not have the final word. Today just like during the time of Apostle Paul, many in the Church are confused regarding the relative timing of the *parousia* and the resurrection. Hence, as Christian's hope should be on what the Scripture says about the end time. Paul's encouragement on the coming of Christ is important because it speaks to the second coming of Christ and sheds a little bit of light on what forever will be like (v.17). If one believes Scripture to be true, and Jesus Christ did die only to rise again (4.14), then there is a (*elpida*) hope, for mankind, until the day of Christ's return to which those who believe will be with him forever and always (4.17). Hence, men of all ages, including the postmodern men, especially believers, must be prepared to be raptured with him.

Findings

Analysis of the nature postmodern society and the pericope used for this study shows that:

1. The postmodern society is dominated by anti-biblical ideas like rejection of absolute truth which threatens the superiority of biblical truths, including rapture.
2. Paul's eschatological discourse in 1Thessalonians 4:15-18 is a force to be reckoned with as it is predicated on the teachings of Jesus.
3. Paul's eschatological discourse was necessitated by the need to encourage the Thessalonian believers who were hopeless about dead saints (Hazen, 2022).

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4. Thessalonian believers were eagerly waiting for the Lord's coming (*parousia*, 1 Thessalonians 1:3, 10)
 5. The *parousia* has its benefits for the Thessalonian believers and the postmodern believers.
 6. The coming of the Lord is eminent.

Discussion

The introduction of this paper calls attention to the dangers of postmodernism like rejection of absolute truth that constitute threats to Christian faith and all its tenets, including rapture. Corroborating this, in a study carried out by Ayomide & Alabi, (2021), some negative traits of postmodern Christians towards rapture were identified and these include: loss of focus about rapture, carefree attitudes towards rapture and adulterating God's Word to fulfill selfish interest. The two scholars concluded that these negative traits imply that postmodern believers' negative attitudes towards rapture are counter-productive and can therefore never groom believers to be rapture-ready (Ayomide & Alabi, 2021). Thus, Paul's eschatological teachings in 1 Thessalonians 4:15-18 is highly needed to prepare the postmodern believers for rapture.

Conclusion

Through Paul's Eschatological Discourse in 1 Thessalonians 4:15-18 analysed thus far, the following inferences for application to the postmodern church can be drawn:

1. Paul's eschatological discourse in the pericope under analysis is a force to be reckoned with as it is predicated on the Lord's own word or revelation, not on human speculation (1 Thessalonians 4:14). As such, postmodern Christians should receive it as the gospel truth allowing it to guide their preparation for the Lord's *parousia*.
2. The need to encourage the Thessalonian believers who were hopeless about dead saints necessitated the eschatological discourse. As Paul counseled the Thessalonian believers not to mourn like unbelievers, the present day believers should stop mourning over those who died in the Lord as they are with the Lord in a much better place right now enjoying freedom from pain, worry, disease and most essentially, sin! (Hazen, 2022).

3. It is also apparent that these Thessalonian believers strongly believed in the *parousia*, the coming of the Lord, as they demonstrated their faith by eagerly awaiting this glorious event (1Thessalonians 1:3, 10). Paul emphasized that the Lord's *parousia* will lead to a reunion between the dead and the living saints.
4. This inestimable event also has two more merits: a) it will help postmodern believers to keep a proper perspective on this life and the one to come (Hazen, 2022). b) Remembering that the Rapture is fast approaching also encourages postmodern believers to live a holy life, knowing that the trumpet could sound at any moment (Hazen, 2022).
5. Predicating on the expression: "any moment now" return of the Lord also encourages a sense of concern for those outside the fold. It creates a sense of urgency to share the love Christ with others and support missions thereby expanding the coast of the Kingdom of God (Hazen, 2022).
6. Lastly, the postmodern church must note that Rapture, *parousia* or the Lord's coming could be the next event on God's prophetic calendar. As such, the present church should be wise to keep eyes and ears open as it will happen when least expected.

Recommendations

In order to enhance Christians of postmodern age to be really rapture-ready, certain steps must be taken. What are these steps in question?

1. Postmodern Christians must be involved in an in-depth study of God's Word; especially, in regards to rapture.
2. Postmodern Christians must also enroll in the school of the Holy Spirit for divine instructions, understanding and guidance on rapture;
3. Postmodern Christians must equally live a consistent biblical life so as to be rapture-ready.
4. Regular self-examination in the light of the gospel is highly necessary.
5. Uncompromising obedience to God's Word should not be handled with levity.
6. Sharing the gospel of Christ with unbelievers must be given priority.
7. Postmodern Christians must regard the Bible as the final authority regardless of the negative features of the postmodern society in which they exist.

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